

Developing Machine Learning Technique for Measuring Central Bank Credibility

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Abstract

The formulation of monetary policy by the central bank in order to achieve the target will only be effective with the presence of credibility. The role of credibility in supporting policy effectiveness has long been believed by economists and central bank practitioners, including determine the ability of central bank to manage the expectation of economic actors.

Empirically, credibility is a qualitative concept, which is not easy to measure. There are several approaches have been used in measuring credibility, including using survey and constructing composite index from several indicators. For Indonesia's case Bank Indonesia regularly conducts survey to external stakeholders to measure the policy credibility. The policy credibility survey is prepared based on 6 (six) aspects of credibility, i.e. formulation, independence, communication, accountability, coordination, and effectiveness. But, in practice, the survey method has several weaknesses for measuring policy credibility.

In this research, we aim to utilize Big Data Analytics method, particularly text mining and machine learning, as an alternative method for measuring stakeholders' perceptions on Bank Indonesia's credibility from news data. Measurement of credibility is done by utilizing machine learning models that are built based on annotated news sentences. From the out-of-sample evaluation results, we achieve an average F1-score of 61.1%. The resulting credibility index also moves in-line with the result of the policy credibility survey, with a correlation of 79.7%.

Keywords – central bank credibility; policy formulation; central bank communication; text mining; machine learning

1 Background

As stated in Act Number 23 of 1999 concerning Bank Indonesia, which was amended by Act Number 3 of 2004 and Act Number 6 of 2009, the objective of Bank Indonesia is to achieve and maintain the stability of the rupiah value. In achieving this objective, Bank Indonesia adapted the Inflation Targeting Framework (ITF), by using interest rates as operational targets. This framework was formally adopted in July 2005, replacing the previous monetary policy using base money as the target.

In the ITF framework, Bank Indonesia's policy will be transmitted through changes in monetary instruments and operational targets to influence a variety of economic and financial variables before finally achieving the ultimate target. The relationship occurs through interactions between the central bank, the banking and financial sectors, and the real sector. Changes in the Bank Indonesia's policy rate (i.e. BI 7-days reverse repo rate / BI 7DRR) affect through various channels: interest rate channel, credit, exchange rate, asset price, and expectation.

The formulation of monetary policy by the central bank in order to achieve the target will only be effective with the presence of credibility. The role of credibility in supporting policy effectiveness has long been believed by economists and central bank practitioners. This is in-line with the existence of rational expectation which is believed to play a role in shaping the behavior of economic agents. The credibility of monetary policy will determine the ability of central bank to manage the expectation of economic actors (Łyziak & Paloviita, 2016) and will be reflected in the expectation of long-term interest rates and other asset prices (Blinder, 2000).

Based on the theory, credibility is about consistency in providing accurate and valuable information or always being responsible (Sobel, 1985). In the terminology of policy makers, credibility is the expectation that policies

that are announced will be implemented, not only reflect the policy makers' wishes, but also reflect the situation and conditions behind the policy so that if there is a shock beyond expectation, it will affect the credibility (Drazen & Masson, 1994). Central bank credibility is formed by 7 (seven) factors that are considered important, i.e. honesty, independence, consistency (history of fighting inflation), transparency, maintaining fiscal deficit, the use of policy rules, and incentives (personal loss) (Blinder, 2000). In a simpler way, credibility can be determined by competence/professionalism, independence, accountability, and transparency.

Central bank credibility also plays a pivotal role in building public's trust on the institution. First, trust is important for reasons of political accountability, ensuring operationally independent central banks are meeting the terms of their social contract with wider society. Another reason to try to build trust is that trust helps manage expectations. But, evidence suggests that public may never engage with central bank communication because it is written in a way that they cannot understand, which contributes to a lack of trust in the central bank as an independent institution (Haldane, Macaulay, & McMahon, Bank of England Staff Working Paper No.847, 2020). As argued in Haldane and McMahon (2018), one of the reasons that a central bank may want to communicate more directly with the general public is to try to build public understanding as a means of establishing trust and credibility about central banks and their policies.

Empirically, credibility is a qualitative concept, which is not easy to measure, and there are several approaches have been used in measuring credibility. In Cukierman & Meltzer (1986) and Faust & Svensson (2001), central bank independence is used as a proxy for credibility. In Blinder (2000), the credibility of a central bank is measured using survey where economists choose the main characteristics that contribute to the central bank credibility, which is then quantified to produce an index. While in Lyziak (2016) measurement is made using an index, which is built from several indicators including the achievement of the central bank's target, the deviation of inflation expectation, transparent targets and indicators, independence, and accountability.

For Indonesia's case, Bank Indonesia regularly conducts survey to external stakeholders to measure the policy credibility, i.e. Bank Indonesia's Policy Credibility Survey. The policy credibility survey is prepared based on 6 (six) aspects of credibility, i.e. formulation, independence, communication, accountability, coordination, and effectiveness.

In practice, the survey method has several weaknesses:

1. **survey fatigue:** respondents experiencing burnout if surveyed repeatedly, so that surveys cannot be carried out too often;
2. **social desirability bias:** respondents giving a response that is favorable for the surveyor, which is Bank Indonesia, hence the survey results are less objective;
3. **recency bias:** respondents generally provide responses based on current policies and/or events, hence the survey results are very dependent on the execution time; and
4. **survey cost & time.**

Based on these factors, it is necessary to strengthen Bank Indonesia's policy credibility measurement method. Utilizing Big Data Analytics to gather public perception regarding central bank policy can be an alternative method that needs to be considered.

This research aims to utilize Big Data Analytics method, particularly text mining and machine learning, to measure stakeholders' perceptions on the central bank credibility from news data. Utilizing the ability of computers to carry out complex analysis (advance analytics) is expected to be able to identify changes in public sentiment towards the credibility of central bank policy. The indicator is expected to be used as an additional measure of central bank credibility and to support the effectiveness of central bank monetary policy in the future.

The paper is organized as follows. In section 2, we provide literature reviews on Bank Indonesia's Policy Credibility Survey and text mining for economic and financial news. In section 3, we discuss the data and methodology. In section 4, we provide a summary of the results and evaluation of the model. In section 5, we conclude the paper and offer some thoughts for future works

2 Literature Review

2.1 Bank Indonesia's Policy Credibility Survey

Since 2013, Bank Indonesia conducts semi-annual survey to external stakeholders to measure the policy credibility, i.e. Bank Indonesia's Policy Credibility Survey, for all 3 (three) sectors of policy: monetary, macro prudential, and payment system. The survey is expected to provide a measure for policy credibility that is objective, accurate, reflecting broad view of stakeholders (including general public), and available timely, which then can be used to determine the effectiveness of policy communication as well as feedback for formulating future policy communication strategies.

The target respondent of the survey is approximately 1,000 respondents in 20 major cities in Indonesia, consist of government, academics, bankers, industry player, and general public. The survey is measuring 6 (six) aspects of credibility:

1. **Formulation:** Bank Indonesia's policy is formulated carefully according to its purpose;
2. **Independence:** Bank Indonesia formulates its policy independently, without intervention from any party;
3. **Communication:** Bank Indonesia's policy has been well communicated to the public;
4. **Accountability:** Bank Indonesia's policies are well accounted for;
5. **Coordination:** Bank Indonesia and the Government always coordinate well; and
6. **Effectiveness:** Bank Indonesia policies are effective in achieving its objectives.

The policy credibility index from the survey will be used as benchmark indicator for measuring the accuracy of the methodology that we developed.

2.2 Text Mining on Economic & Financial News

Text data have been widely used for research in economics and finance. Nowadays, text mining algorithms are growing rapidly along with the adoption of big data and machine learning. These algorithms can automatically "read" and "extract" relevant information from the text, such as the person's name, the organization's name, and the keywords. Compared to the manual way, text mining allows us to make use of much larger text data than press releases, including news and social media.

Sahminan (2008) identified keywords that reflect a tight, neutral, or loose monetary policy inclination in the press release statement of Bank Indonesia over the period from January 2004 to December 2007. The econometric analysis shows that monetary policy statements that contain loose or neutral policy inclination tend to lower interbank interest rates, while monetary policy statements with tight policy inclination tend to have no impact on interbank interest rates (asymmetric effect).

Bollen et al. (2011) proved that the mood expressed by Twitter users can be analyzed to improve the stock market prediction. Moods are identified using keywords, e.g. "I feel ..." and "I'm ...", and then categorized into different types of mood by using OpinionFinder and Google-Profile of Mood States (GPOMS). Similar to Bollen et al. (2011), O'Connor et al. (2010) created a public sentiment index from positive and negative word occurrences in economic related tweets. This index correlated with the Gallup's

Economic Confidence Index at 73.1% and with the Index of Consumer Sentiment (ICS) from the Reuters/University at 63.5%.

In addition to social media data, news data are also widely used to analyze economic conditions. Baker et al. (2015) developed an Economic Policy Uncertainty (EPU) index by using news articles from 10 leading U.S. newspapers. The EPU index reflects the frequency of articles that contain the following trio of terms: economic ("economic" or "economy"); policy ("Congress," "deficit," "Federal Reserve," "legislation," "regulation," or "White House), and uncertainty ("uncertain" or "uncertainty"). The EPU indexes have also been constructed for 11 other countries with list of keywords that are tailored to the language and economy.

In terms of monetary policy, Tobback et al. (2017) developed the Hawkish-Dovish (HD) index that measures media's perception of ECB communications. The HD index is computed by using two methods: semantic orientation (SO) and support vector machine (SVM). The HD index based on SO method is computed by counting the co-occurrences of strings with a fixed set or pre-determined words/expressions that are normally associated with "hawkish" and "dovish" concepts to determine the tone of the document. For the SVM method, instead of using predefined set of keywords, the algorithm automatically looks for patterns in text documents to select the words with the highest discriminative power and determines the tone of a document based on them. Similar Hawkish-Dovish research has also been done earlier by Lucca & Trebbi (2009) for the FOMC statements.

In our previous research (Zulen & Wibisono, 2018), we developed a new measure of stakeholders' expectation on Bank Indonesia's policy rate. From methodological perspective, we showed how to utilize news articles data to develop the new measure, by employing machine learning-based technique. The expectations are extracted from news, starting from 14 days before the monthly Board of Governor's meeting. Based on out-of-sample evaluation result, the policy rate expectation index from news is potential to be used as a new measure of policy rate expectation.

3 Methodology

We develop machine learning methodology for extracting policy credibility information from news data through 6 (six) steps as shown in Figure 1.

In this research, we will focus on 4 (four) credibility aspects, out of 6 (six) aspects that are measured using

Figure 1. Workflow for Policy Credibility Extraction using Machine Learning

survey. Based on our preliminary observations on a number of news articles, there are only very few news related to accountability, communication, and independence aspects. The communication aspect will be calculated based on the conformity between public expectations on the direction of monetary policy and forward guidance in Bank Indonesia’s press release after each of the monthly Board of Governor meeting. Meanwhile, the independence aspect is combined with the coordination aspect.

3.1 Data Collection

The news data used in this research are obtained from Bank Indonesia’s Cyber Library, which is a curated internal repository of news articles related to economic and financial topics. The news articles data are available on a daily basis since 1999. The news data used in this research are from January 2010 to August 2019.

News articles collected from Bank Indonesia’s Cyber Library are not entirely relevant for measuring policy credibility. So, we do data filtering to filter out news that are not relevant. The news articles must contain one of the keywords related to monetary policy: “Inflation”, “Monetary”, “Exchange rate”, “Current account”, “Policy rate”, “BI Rate”, “BI 7-days reverse repo rate”, and their variations in writing. News are the split into sentences for further processing.

3.2 Data Preprocessing

Each sentence is transformed from textual format into format that can be processed by machine learning model (numerical format), following the steps below:

1. **sentence cleansing**: lowercasing, replacing synonyms, numbers, and common names in the sentence;
2. **tokenization**: splitting sentence into words/tokens;

3. **n-gram vectorization**: creating n consecutive words (n -gram) as additional features; and

4. **sparse terms removal**: removing rarely occurring terms from the feature list.

An example of data preprocessing on a sentence is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Example of Data Preprocessing Result

3.3 Data Annotation

Text mining that make uses of machine learning techniques require annotated datasets for training dan testing the machine learning model. Annotation is the process of attaching additional information into a collection of texts. Annotation is needed to "teach" the text mining algorithm how to extract the information from the texts, so that the process can be done automatically in the future.

In this research, annotation is done on sentence-level, as the smallest data unit. We added categorical information on sentiment for each credibility aspect to each sentence. Table 1 shows all possible labels of annotation for each credibility aspect. This categorical information will be used as target class in machine learning algorithms.

The annotators were from related departments in Bank Indonesia, i.e. Economic & Monetary Policy Department, Statistics Department, Strategic Management & Governance Department, and Communication Department. Each sentence was annotated by 3 (three) annotators to minimize human error and subjectivity. The label for each sentence is chosen based on majority vote, or based on joint discussion if there is no majority vote. We also provided an annotation guidance so that all annotators have similar understanding and the annotations can be given consistently.

Table 1. Possible Labels for Each Credibility Aspect

No.	Credibility Aspect	Possible Labels
1.	Formulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive : 1 • Negative : -1 • Not Relevant : -
2.	Effectiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive : 1 • Negative : -1 • Not Relevant : -
3.	Coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive : 1 • Negative : -1 • Not Relevant : -
4.	Expectation / Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hawkish : 1 • Neutral : 0 • Dovish : -1 • Not Relevant : -

In total, we collected 12,560 sentences that have been annotated. Table 2 shows the distribution of annotated sentences for each credibility aspect and possible label. Table 3 shows some samples of annotated sentences for each credibility aspect.

3.4 Model Construction

As we can see from the annotation results (Table 2), the target class distribution for each credibility aspect is quite imbalanced. In order to ease the modeling and improve the accuracy of the model, with imbalanced data as consideration, classification step is carried out in 2 (two) stages for each credibility aspect:

1. Classification on whether the sentence contains credibility information (credibility vs. non-credibility); and
2. Classification on the sentiment of the credibility in the sentence (positive vs. negative, hawkish vs. neutral vs. dovish).

With this configuration, in total there are 8 (eight) machine learning models constructed, i.e. 2 models for each aspect.

As for the datasets, the preprocessing results from step 2 (section 3.2) and annotation labels from step 3 (section 3.3) are combined to become dataset for the machine learning model (as illustrated in Figure 3). In other words, sentences that have been transformed into numerical vectors and annotated (1 line = 1 sentence) are used as input for machine learning algorithms.

$$\hat{f}_1(\text{sentence_vector}) \in \{\text{credibility}, \text{noncredibility}\}$$

$$\hat{f}_2(\text{sentence_vector}) \in \{\text{positive / hawkish}, \text{neutral}, \text{negative / dovish}\}$$

The dataset is split into 2 (two) datasets: training dataset and test dataset using 92:8 ratios. Training dataset is used to build the classification model. Test dataset is used in model evaluation to provide unbiased evaluation on the model.

The training on machine learning models is carried out on using 6 (six) machine learning models, 300 (three hundred) model configurations, and 5 (five) folds of train-test split to find the best classification model for solving the task. The machine learning models that we used are:

1. **Logistic regression**: modeled the linear relationship between independent variables and the expectation category as dependent variable;
2. **Naïve bayes**: modeled the probability of expectation category based on Bayes' theorem with the independence assumptions between predictors;
3. **Decision tree**: modeled the decision tree that predict expectation category (represented in the leaves) based on a set of decision rules (represented in the branches);
4. **Random forest**: combined the predictions of multiple decision trees with bootstrapping aggregation;
5. **XGBoost**: an implementation of gradient boosted tree by DMLC (<http://dmlc.ml/>); and
6. **Deep learning**: a type of machine learning that is inspired by the structure of a human brain by using a multi-layered structure of algorithms called neural networks.

Figure 3. Dataset Illustration

Table 2. Distribution of Annotated Sentences

No.	Credibility Aspect	Total Annotated Sentences	Percentage (%)	Possible Labels
1.	Formulation	1,955	15.6%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive : 1,595 (81.6%) • Negative : 360 (18.4%)
2.	Effectiveness	2,554	20.3%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive : 2,072 (81.1%) • Negative : 482 (18.9%)
3.	Coordination	349	2.8%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive : 303 (86.8%) • Negative : 46 (13.2%)
4.	Expectation / Communication	1,790	14.3%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hawkish : 493 (27.6%) • Neutral : 706 (39.4%) • Dovish : 391 (33.0%)
5.	Not Relevant	5,912	47.0%	

Table 3. Sample of Annotated Sentences

No	Sentence	Credibility Aspect	Label
1.	<i>BI juga memutuskan untuk mempertahankan suku bunga acuan karena masih terdapat sejumlah risiko eksternal dan domestik yang perlu diwaspadai.</i>	Formulation	<i>Positive</i>
2.	<i>Dari kebijakan pengelolaan nilai tukar yang “keliru” dari BI tersebut, Rupiah terdepresiasi 75% lebih sejak September 2011 lalu atau sekitar 15% depresiasi per tahun.</i>	Formulation	<i>Negative</i>
3.	<i>Kenaikan suku bunga acuan Bank Indonesia berhasil membuat rupiah menguat.</i>	Effectiveness	<i>Positive</i>
4.	<i>Sementara itu dari sektor konstruksi, Sekretaris Perusahaan PT Wika Suradi menilai meskipun BI Rate telah diturunkan, tingkat suku bunga kredit perbankan di Indonesia saat ini sangat tidak kompetitif.</i>	Effectiveness	<i>Negative</i>
5.	<i>Kebijakan ini juga sejalan dengan keinginan pemerintah dan Bank Indonesia untuk mengelola defisit transaksi berjalan ke arah yang lebih sehat.</i>	Coordination	<i>Positive</i>
6.	<i>Sebagian kalangan menilai ada tekanan politik terhadap otoritas moneter untuk menurunkan BI Rate berkaitan dengan ambisi pemerintah mengejar pertumbuhan ekonomi 5,7%, kendati dugaan ini dibantah berkali-kali oleh Gubernur BI Agus Martowardojo.</i>	Coordination	<i>Negative</i>
7.	<i>Maka, sepanjang tahun 2013 ini potensi kenaikan BI rate masih terbuka maksimal sebesar 50 bps.</i>	Expectation / Communication	<i>Hawkish</i>
8.	<i>Kepala Ekonom Samuel Sekuritas Lana Soelistianingsih mengatakan BI rate pada tahun ini masih bisa ditahan pada level 5,75 persen senada dengan tahun sebelumnya, dengan syarat tidak ada kenaikan dari sisi inflasi.</i>	Expectation / Communication	<i>Neutral</i>
9.	<i>“Jika inflasi sudah mulai terkendali maka kemungkinan BI rate akan kembali turun,” terangnya.</i>	Expectation / Communication	<i>Dovish</i>

3.5 Text Classification

The machine learning models that have been constructed in previous step is then applied to classify the policy credibility from sentence vectors that act as the input, according the 2 (two) stages we've explained in section 3.4. The result of the sentiment classification will be used to calculate policy credibility index.

3.6 Index Calculation

The final result of this research is Bank Indonesia's policy credibility index, that can be produced in various frequency: monthly, quarterly, semi-annually, annually. The index is calculated for each policy credibility aspect, and then combined into aggregate index.

3.6.1 Policy Credibility Index for Formulation, Effectiveness, and Coordination Aspects

The policy credibility index for formulation, effectiveness, and coordination aspects (*index*) is calculated as a net balance of the number of positive and negative sentences related to the aspect (*aspect*) in a time period (*t*).

$$index_{aspect,t} = \frac{\#positive_{aspect,t} - \#negative_{aspect,t}}{\#positive_{aspect,t} + \#negative_{aspect,t}}$$

The policy credibility index for the 3 (three) aspects has following characteristics:

1. Range of index: [-100%,100%].
2. The index will be close to 100% if there are more news with positive sentiment on the policy credibility aspect.

The index will be close to -100% if there are more news with negative sentiment on the policy credibility aspect.

3. Positive index means more news with with positive sentiment on the policy credibility aspect compared to the negative ones.

Zero index means equal number of news with positive sentiment and negative sentiment on the policy credibility aspect.

Negative index means more news with negative sentiment on the policy credibility aspect compared to the positive ones.

4. If $index_{t1} > index_{t2}$ then the proportion of news with positive sentiment on the policy credibility aspect is greater in *t1* than in *t2*.

If $index_{t1} < index_{t2}$ then the proportion of news with negative sentiment on the policy credibility aspect is greater in *t1* than in *t2*.

3.6.2 Policy Credibility Index for Communication Aspect

The expectation index for communication aspect (*index*) is calculated as a net balance of the number sentences with hawkish, neutral and dovish expectations on the direction of monetary policy in a time period (*t*).

$$index_{expectation,t} = \frac{\#hawkish_t - \#dovish_t}{\#hawkish_t + \#neutral_t + \#dovish_t}$$

The expectation index has following characteristics:

1. Range of index: [-100%,100%].
2. The index will be close to 100% if there are more news with hawkish expectation on the monetary policy.

The index will be close to -100% if there are more news with dovish expectation on the monetary policy.

3. Positive index means more news with hawkish expectation on the monetary policy compared to the dovish ones.

Zero index means equal number news with hawkish and dovish expectation on the monetary policy

Negative index means more news with dovish expectation on the monetary policy compared to the hawkish ones.

4. If $index_{t1} > index_{t2}$ then the proportion of news with hawkish expectation on the monetary policy is greater in *t1* than in *t2*.

If $index_{t1} < index_{t2}$ then the proportion of news with dovish expectation on the monetary policy is greater in *t1* than in *t2*.

The policy credibility index for communication aspect (*index_{communication}*) is calculated as difference between public expectations on the direction of monetary policy (*index_{expectation}*) and forward guidance (*FwdGuidance*) in Bank Indonesia's press release after the monthly Board of Governor meeting in a time period (*t*).

$$index_{communication,t} = 1 - |FwdGuidance_t - index_{expectation,t}|$$

The policy credibility index for communication aspect has following characteristics:

1. Range of index: [-100%,100%].
2. The index will be close to 100% if public expectation on monetary policy is more in line with Bank Indonesia's forward guidance.

The index will be close to -100% if public expectation on monetary policy is not in line with Bank Indonesia's forward guidance.

3. Positive index means public expectation on monetary policy is in line with Bank Indonesia's forward guidance.

Negative index means public expectation on monetary policy is not in line with Bank Indonesia's forward guidance.

4. If $index_{t1} > index_{t2}$ then public expectation on monetary policy is more in line with Bank Indonesia's forward guidance in *t1* than in *t2*.

If $index_{t1} < index_{t2}$ then public expectation on monetary policy is more not in line with Bank Indonesia's forward guidance in *t1* than in *t2*.

3.6.3 Aggregate Policy Credibility Index

The aggregate credibility index (**Credibility Index**) is the average of the credibility indices from the 4 (four) credibility aspects (***index_{aspect}***) in a time period (***t***).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Credibility Index}_t &= \frac{1}{4} x \\ &= \frac{1}{4} \sum_{\text{aspect} \in \{\text{formulation, effectiveness, coordination, communication}\}} (\text{index}_{\text{aspect}, t}) \end{aligned}$$

The characteristics of the aggregate policy credibility index are the same with the characteristics explained in section 3.6.1

4 Result & Analysis

4.1 Machine Learning Model Evaluation

Classification models that have been trained in the previous steps need to be evaluated in order to measure their accuracy in predicting the target class (i.e. policy credibility), and eventually choose the best classification model for each credibility aspect. To measure the accuracy of classification and comparison between models, the results of the classification in the test dataset are compared with the results of the annotations as illustrated in the confusion matrix (Table 4). We use F1-score as metric for evaluation, in order to get a balanced classification model with the optimal balance of recall and precision. Besides F1-score, we also calculate Accuracy, Precision, dan Recall score as additional evaluation metrics.

Each evaluation metric is defined as follows:

1. **Accuracy:** Percentage of the accuracy of classification model.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{(TP + TN)}{\text{Total}}$$

2. **Precision:** Percentage of the accuracy for sentences identified as credibility.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{(TP + FP)}$$

3. **Recall:** Percentage of identified credibility sentences.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{(TP + FN)}$$

4. **F1:** The tradeoff (harmonic mean) between precision and recall.

$$F1 = \frac{(2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall})}{(\text{Precision} + \text{Recall})}$$

Table 4. Confusion Matrix for Evaluation

		Annotation Result		
		Non-Credibility	Credibility – Positive	Credibility – Negative
Classification Result	Non-Credibility	TN	FN	FN
	Credibility – Positive	FP	TP	FP
	Credibility – Negative	FP	FP	TP

TP = True Positive TN = True Negative

FP = False Positive FN = False Negative

The result of out-of-sample evaluation for each policy credibility aspect are given in Table 5. We achieve a good machine learning model for coordination aspect (F1=69.9%, Best ML Model: FastText) and communication aspect (F1=65.6%, Best ML Model: Logistic Regression) aspect. Meanwhile, model for formulation aspect (F1=54.0%, Best ML Model: Logistic Regression) and effectiveness aspect (F1=54.8%, Best ML Model: Logistic Regression) can be further developed to achieve better result. The overall F1-score (average from all credibility aspects) is 61.1%.

4.2 Result Evaluation

For result evaluation, we calculate the correlation between policy credibility index generated from news using Big Data Analytics and from our survey. Graphs of both indices from are presented in Figure 4.

Both indices are generally moving in the same direction, with a correlation of 79.7%. The correlation value indicates that the policy credibility index from news is potential to be used as a new measure of Bank Indonesia's policy credibility.

Table 5. Classification Model Evaluation Result

Credibility Aspect	% Credibility from Annotation	Best Machine Learning Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Formulation	15.6%	Logistic Regression	78.6%	55.7%	52.5%	54.0%
Effectiveness	20.3%	Logistic Regression	71.0%	48.7%	62.6%	54.8%
Coordination	2.8%	FastText	86.0%	80.6%	61.8%	69.9%
Expectation	14.3%	Logistic Regression	86.6%	63.3%	68.1%	65.6%
Average	13.5%	-	80.6%	62,1%	61.3%	61.1%

Figure 4. Comparison between Policy Credibility Index from News and from Survey

The resulting policy credibility index can also capture various events related to Bank Indonesia’s policy credibility. Figure 5 showcased several highlight events:

1. **2nd semester of 2013:** Consecutive increases in Bank Indonesia’s policy rate had impact in suppressing economic growth (**Formulation**);
2. **1st semester of 2015:** Government asked Bank Indonesia to cut the policy rate for supporting economic growth (**Coordination**);
3. **2nd semester of 2016:** Bank Indonesia transformed its policy rate from BI Rate into BI 7-days Reverse Repo Rate (BI-7DRR) to speed up monetary transmission (**Formulation**); and
4. **1st semester of 2019:** Inflation is under control and exchange rates relatively stable (**Effectiveness**).

Figure 5. Event Analysis

5 Conclusion & Future Work

5.1 Conclusion

In this research, we develop a new measure of stakeholders’ expectation on Bank Indonesia’s policy rate. From methodological perspective, we show how to utilize news articles data to develop the new measure, by employing machine learning-based technique. The expectations are extracted from news, starting from 14 days before the monthly Board of Governor’s meeting. The machine learning model is trained by using sentences that have been annotated manually.

From out-of-sample evaluation, we achieve an F1-score of 76.8% on classification accuracy by using logistic regression model. The resulting monthly expectation index has 78.6% correlation with the expectation index generated from Bloomberg’s monthly survey.

In this research, we develop a new methodology for measuring Bank Indonesia's policy credibility by utilizing news articles data and machine learning-based technique. From the out-of-sample evaluation results, we achieve an average F1-score of 61.1%, with better scores for coordination and communication aspects, while models for formulation and effectiveness aspects can be further developed to improve their accuracy.

The resulting policy credibility index also moves in-line with the policy credibility index generated from our survey, with a correlation of 79.7%. The correlation value indicates that the policy credibility index from news is potential to be used as a new measure of Bank Indonesia's policy credibility.

5.2 Future Work

There are several improvements in the methodology that can be applied for works ahead:

1. Data Source Addition

The addition of new data sources, particularly English news, can be useful to enrich the data sources and capture additional perceptions by foreign stakeholders on Bank Indonesia's policy credibility.

2. Classification Model for English News

After we acquire the English news data, we need to develop the text mining model for English language to extract the policy credibility information.

3. Opinion Holder Identification

Currently, we haven't developed text mining model to identify the opinion holder, i.e. person / organization / other entities that stated their perception on Bank Indonesia's policy credibility in the news articles. If we have developed the model, we can group the result by the institutional group of the opinion holder, e.g. government, authorities, banking, capital market, industry, academics, and general public. Thus, we can develop targeted policy communication strategy for each group.

Acknowledgements

This paper and the research behind it would not have been possible without the support from our colleagues in Statistics Department, Economic & Monetary Policy Department, Strategic Management & Governance Department, Communication Department, and Bank Indonesia Institute.

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